

Situation Analysis of Digital Literacy of the Teachers of Children with Multiple Disabilities

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: April 25, 2021</p> <p>Accepted: September 30, 2021</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : Digital Literacy, Education, Teachers, Competencies.</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.5828278</p>	<p><i>Digital literacy refers to the capacity to use information and communications technologies securely and critically for work. Using computers to search, evaluate, create, present, and share information over the Internet is one of the most important aspects of modern literacy. Digital literacy is one of the fundamental competencies of a modern person, and acquiring knowledge and skills in the field of ICT is one of the criteria for successful social inclusion in current society and the labor market. As a result, these two notions have become part of the educational system to accomplish quality education. Teachers' and students' roles and the resources utilized in teaching, and the nature of teacher instruction have all changed due to the notions of ICT application and digital literacy in the educational process. From digital literacy to curriculum alignment, the teacher's tasks are various to make adjustments insufficient, including their knowledge and abilities linked to the use of technology and recognizing the relationship between technology, techniques, and content.</i></p>

Introduction

Eshet (2004) stated that the rapid development of information and communication technology ICT (Information and Communication Technology) was affected by a massive digital revolution, making digital literacy one of the important issues in today's digital education. As a result, it's not unexpected that many schools and educational institutions have begun to restructure their curricula to include digital literacy. Teachers and their ongoing training are critical for any effective classroom reforms.

Teachers' jobs have gotten more demanding in this regard since, in addition to strengthening students' existing knowledge and abilities, they must also develop new ones. To successfully apply new methods in the classroom, students must enhance their digital literacy. When it comes to curriculum revisions in this digital era, concur that teachers' assistance is necessary (Voogt & Roblin, 2010).

Definition of Digital Literacy

Digital literacy, according to UNESCO (2011), is an umbrella concept that incorporates abilities such as Information and Communication Technology (ICT), information literacy, and technological literacy, all of which are used interchangeably but have various meanings. ICT literacy states to the user's capability to participate in a civilization wherever "facilities and cultural contributions are computer sported and internet. "Information literacy focuses on the capacity to use digital information effectively, i.e., knowing how to identify, locate, and process all digital information, whereas technological literacy is concerned with a more profound grasp of technology and includes operator and technical computer abilities.

Digital literacy is a "individuals' awareness, attitude, and ability to use digital tools and facilities to identify access effectively, manage, integrate, evaluate, synthesize, and interact with others in the context of specific life situations (Martin & Grudziecki, 2006).

The Department of Education (1996) defines digital literacy as the capability to use computers and other technologies to promote productivity, performance, and learning, while Barrette (2001) claims that it includes two components: control basic computer and understanding thinking skills and problem-solving. According to Nascimbeni (2018), digital literacy has two dimensions: useful and critical. The functional component includes competencies and skills that enable everyone to write, read, and communicate utilizing various media, technologies, and platforms, as well as acquire digital literacy and sustain professional and educational online interactions.

Digital literacy as "the ability to use computers at an adequate level for creation, communication, and collaboration in a literate society," whereas Dudeney, Hockly, & Pegrum (2014) defined it as "the ability to use technologies at one's disposal and understanding the social practices that surround the use of new media." The critical dimension, on the other way, emphasizes the non-neutral nature of digital tools and surroundings, as well as the fact that digital resources are frequently used for community mechanisms and segregation (Spitzer,

2016). This component is most significant as of the possible risks associated with the usage of social media and the internet (Holloway et al. 2013, Spitzer 2016) and societal dynamics such as privacy issues, private data organization, and online repute managing (O'Neil, 2016).

Teachers Role and Digital Era

Teachers' tasks have grown increasingly complex in this ever-changing world of boundless knowledge. Today's instructors are expected to become more technology (Savvy & Amin, 2016). More traitors, critical, independent open-minded experts, and originators will assist students in evaluating the use of new sources in the digital environment. As a result, it's no surprise that "teachers in this digital age face new obstacles every day in terms of students, their particular demands, new technology and software, and their own developing needs." Current students are always "on," and as digital natives who learn and think differently, they use Facebook, Twitter, Instagram, and a slew of other apps on their phones and tablets, making it problematic for teachers to pay attention in class (Sharma, 2017).

The ability of modern teachers to establish classrooms and collaborative work, create new learning environments, and combine new pedagogy with technology is critical to the effective addition of new technologies into the classroom. A unique combination of teacher abilities is required for all of these, including frequent use of technology to encourage digital literacy and knowledge (Al Khateeb, 2017).

Statement of the problem

This study was to analyze digital literacy regarding the teachers of children with disabilities. It explores the influences of digital literacy for a future researcher in the life field. This study consumes the following objectives; 1) to explore the current awareness of teachers about digital literacy for children with disabilities, 2) to be aware of the importance of digital literacy for the teachers of children with disabilities, and 3) to recognize the influences of digital literacy in education for children with disabilities. Following were the questions whose answer needs to be clarified through this research; 1) what is the current situation of digital literacy used in special education institutes? 2) What are the imperfections left behind during the use of digital literacy for the teachers of children with disabilities, 3) what are the common types of digital literacy that are currently used in special education schools? and 4) what are the influences of digital literacy on the teachers of students with disabilities?

Literature Review

A significant concern is a necessity for the professional training for the teachers of visually impaired children (VIC) in the usage of fresh technologies and their capacity to teach and support pupils in computer use. According to Kelley (1998), one key difficulty for educators is that persons could not be completely awake of developments. Visiting teachers need to be taught new technologies to the point of expertise to encourage pupils with vision impairments to use them (Kelley, 1998).

Microsoft Word, the maximum extensive usage of word processing software, is utilized by many partially sighted persons and blind all over the world. According to the Corn & Wall (2002) study, 69.7% of people with low vision use this program every day.

Corn and Wall (2002) stated that numerous screen reader software products are compatible with Microsoft Word. Practically all training programs for the visually impaired teach professionals how to use it. As a result, the software consumes recognized himself as a significant instrument in communication and education for visually impaired persons. Most of the 410 teachers of visually impaired pupils who took part in the Corn & Wall (2002) study were confident in their ability to use word processing applications (92.1 percent), 81.7 percent in using email, and 70.1 percent in using the internet for personal use.

Color perception problems affect most visually challenged people, limiting their capacity to detect simple color mixtures. The most prevalent color recognition flaw is the failure to detect red and green. We must avoid mixing these two colors in the same working area to lessen the chance of reading difficulties caused by poor color discrimination. In recent years, vision studies have paid more attention to the contrast component (Rubin & Legge, 1989).

Low-vision readers care about two characteristics of contrast: contrast degree and contrast polarization (the difference among light text on a black backdrop or the opposite (Rubin & Legge, 1989)

Capacity (color purity) is a characteristic of color strength that distinguishes it from black, white, or grey of equivalent lightness. The brilliance or cleanliness of color is measured by saturation. There is no grey in pure color. Blue-pink, similar to grey but lacks chromatic purity, is a model of color with no chromatic cleanliness. The chromatic purity of blue is equivalent to lightness with pink- blue is higher. Color perception problems can be congenital or acquired, making it difficult to distinguish colors based on their capacity. This is particularly true for colors of exact types, and it is dependent on the kind of color perception deficiency (Arditi, 1999).

Digital literacy for Multiple Disabilities

The range and intensity of many children's disabilities may influence community inclusion, knowledge, and information needs due to connections with bodily, informational, and socio-cultural obstacles (Kuper & Dixon, 2016). An empirical learning sequence like White's (2019) can help lecturers of students with

disabilities who want to communicate digital literacy understand how this competence develops for preparation and teaching purposes. Education developments are a sort of learning that takes place over time within a subject to demonstrate how improved complexity in thought and skills could be predicted to grow with the support of a teacher. Rather than being matched to grade and age equal companion without disabilities, a person with varying levels of competence or knowledge can be focused on attaining the following stage in the knowledge process (Heritage, 2008). Experiential learning progressions rely on statistical data analysis to plan probable learning routes for the individuals signified in the data sample. The empirical digital literacy learning sequence developed by White (2019) has been authenticated for usage with the person with disabilities of any gender, age, or harshness, with MDVI (White & Poed, 2017).

Teacher's Skills for Digital Literacy

According to Payton and Hague (2010), instructors must be able to produce, locate, and transmit knowledge critically and creatively; therefore, they proposed a roadmap for integrating digital literacy in teaching and a pedagogical framework that includes the following components:

1. Functional abilities that are necessary for the development of basic ICT competency and that may be applied by all learners;
2. Creativity in how students generate and spread knowledge by using blogs, videos, e-books, podcasts, wikis, and other digital platforms to develop their digital literacy.
3. Collaboration and communication by way of a key section of digital literacy in the classroom for facilitating discourse, discussion, and idea exchange;
4. The capability to find and select material, which are essential skills for students' knowledge development and knowledge in a numerical world;
5. Analyzing and altering information to create new knowledge is a major component of digital literacy, as is critical thinking and evaluation.
6. Social and cultural understanding abilities are vital for pupils to increase comprehension while producing meaning through digital literacy.
7. E-safety, which is a component of digital literacy, is important for students' protection in the digital world when they create and share digital information with the assistance of teachers.

In the same way, Sharma (2017) highlights similar skills needed for teachers to play their role as facilitators of learning in a digital era, such as networking skills, communications skills, thinking skills, nurturing skills, and the skill of management of knowledge. Networking skills are necessary for classes in a digital environment because they facilitate collaborative learning of students and teachers. Communication skills assist students in developing technological skills such as making online content or small videos and expanding their ability to reach out to a large community of people via the Internet to share their ideas, projects and chat with many students from other countries.

Sharma (2017), on the other hand, emphasizes that logical skills such as problem-solving, creativity, and originality are important for any modern teacher who wishes to increase digital literacy and incorporate new technology into pedagogical practice. Nurturing skills is reflected in the fact that teachers have to focus on the students' interests and teach them how to connect to others and transmit and share knowledge, helping learners face all challenges in the learning process. Finally, the skill of management of knowledge helps teachers to find, analyze, evaluate, use any information and to correlate students' needs.

Researches Related to the Teacher's Digital Literacy

Daily changes in education, where technology has become additional teaching material, contribute to an enlarged number of researches about how teachers struggle with the experiments, their level of digital literacy, and how it can be more improved (Srivastava & Dey, 2018).

Garcia-Perez, Rebollo-Catalan, and Garcia-Perez (2016) found that numerous general education instructors had a modest degree of digital literacy while using digital technologies. But, it's fascinating that digital literacy was found to be desired with the main objectives of the school curriculum to achieve educational goals in the present digital environment.

In this regard, Rokenes & Krumsvik (2016) found that the growth of teachers' digital literacy depends on reproduction, approaches, linking philosophies with repetition, support, and possessions, receiving different learning approaches, and cooperative learning in their education and research with teachers. Digital literacy of English language instructors found that they have great ranks of digital skills and a willingness to improve their understanding and control of digital practices (Cote & Milliner, 2018).

The language teachers from Finland and UAS, who participated in their research, had a huge importance in their classes' digital elements. About 50% of teachers answered that their digital skills were good or very good. Still, the weakest skill common to all teachers was that they didn't participate enough in digital educational communities. Also, these teachers highlighted the same problems for professional development, such as pedagogical and technical training, the need for time and especially, local support related to their constantly digital training (Juurakko & Nelson, 2018).

According to the study's conclusions, maximum instructors are not digitally proficient in the values and stages required to be excellent digital teachers in today's civilization and school. Similarly, like in other mentioned research, it was noticed that teachers, generally, still don't advance in digital education because of lack of prior knowledge, huge lack of training, and inexperience (Al Khateeb, 2017)

Perceptions of teachers of the public university in Turkey using statistical techniques and tests found that cognitive, social, and technical factors and attitudes were important predictors of teachers' digital literacy. Likewise, it was observed that many teachers had positive and high perceptions of digital literacy. Still, open-ended questions drew attention to their lack of cognitive skills to find some information, create, evaluate, and communicate, which are the principal characteristics of digital literacy (Ata & Yildirim, 2019).

Finally, explaining the consequences of the study about teachers' digital literacy courses should be included in all teacher education programs. Alongside theoretical courses, more practical activities should be included useful for developing teachers' digital literacy (Ata & Yildirim, 2019).

Research Methodology

The research design for this study is the survey method. It is a Quantitative study by its nature. A questionnaire was used to find out the facts and figures. This research study is about situation analysis of awareness of assistive technology of teachers for children with disabilities. All the teachers working in Govt school of Punjab in special education are part of our population. The sample was drawn based on simple random sampling. The data from 200 teachers teaching in Government schools (Special Education) was collected through Google form because of the closure of schools due to COVID-19.

Instrumentation

A self-made questionnaire was used to collect data on Google form because of the school's closure due to COVID-19 privilege in Punjab.

Data collection and analysis

Data was collected online through Google docs, and collected data is tabulated & analyzed by using the SPSS software. Descriptive and inferential statistics were run to draw the results. Frequencies and percentages are calculated to present the demographic items and questions. An independent sample t-test and One-way ANOVA were carried out to represent the difference of opinions in the teachers based on different demographic variables. Based on the results, conclusions were found, and recommendations were made.

Table 1
Sample Description on the Basis of Demographics

Sr#	Description	Frequency (f)	Percentage (%)
Gender			
1	Male	85	85
2	Female	115	115
	Total	200	200
Designation			
1	SSET	53	53
2	JSET	16	16
3	Educator	28	28
6	Other	103	103
	Total	200	200
Residential Area			
1	Rural	63	63
2	Urban	137	137
	Total	200	200
Experience			
1	1-5 Years	17	17
2	6-10 Years	109	109
3	11-15 Years	72	72
4	More	2	2
	Total	200	200
Division			
1	Lahore Division	12	12
2	Multan Division	33	33

3	Rawalpindi Division	29	29
4	Sargodha Division	22	22
5	Bahawalpur Division	19	19
6	D.G Khan Division	22	22
7	Faisalabad Division	19	19
8	Gujranwala Division	30	30
9	Sahiwal Division	14	14
	Total	200	200

Table 2
Section-1: Teacher awareness about Digital Literacy

Sr.#	Statements of Questions	Yes	No	To some extent	M	SD
		f (%)	f (%)	f (%)		
1	Digital literacy is compulsory to become digital nation	178(178)	20(20)	2(2)	1.12	0.35
2	Computer literacy is distinct from digital literacy.	131(131)	45(45)	24(24)	1.46	0.7
3	We can all gain greatly from the digital world.	110(110)	42(42)	48(48)	1.69	0.83
4	Platforms for connecting and collaborating are provided by digital literacy.	135(135)	33(33)	32(32)	1.54	0.76
5	Digital literacy entails being aware of the accepted standards of behavior in online settings.	127(127)	37(37)	36(36)	1.54	0.78
6	Along with reading, writing, and mathematics, digital literacy is the fourth pillar of a child's education	128(128)	36(36)	36(36)	1.54	0.78
7	Children are vulnerable to criminals on digital platforms, especially during the lockdown and social isolation.	112(112)	58(58)	30(30)	1.59	0.73
8	It allows people to learn about new and significant concerns while also enabling creativity in previously unthinkable ways	120(120)	49(49)	29(29)	1.55	0.78

Table 3
Section-2: Teachers' digital literacy and implications

Sr.#	Statements of Questions	Agree f (%)	Disagree f (%)	Undecided f (%)	M	SD
1	The online environment allows teachers to feel at ease while working on their lessons in digital literacy.	188(188)	4(4)	8(8)	4.45	0.67
2	Students should be able to use digital media and online technologies that are significant to them rather than following a prescribed path.	176(176)	4(4)	20(20)	4.14	0.7
3	Human-machine interaction differs significantly from the human-to-human interaction promoted in communicative language schools.	173(173)	5(5)	22(22)	4.11	0.89
4	New technologies necessitate new methods of thinking as well as teaching. You may be an excellent user of modern technology as a teacher.	154(154)	18(18)	28(28)	4.02	0.95
5	Even students may confront challenges when communicating, discovering, and navigating in an online and digital environment with the help of digital literacy.	149(149)	29(29)	22(22)	3.91	1.1
6	The implications of digital literacy aid in meeting the increasing demands for learning that these digital contexts are generating.	143(143)	24(24)	33(33)	3.81	1
7	The significance of digital literacy raises the stakes for being fluent in them, making them essential to the teaching and learning process.	145(145)	25(25)	30(30)	3.96	4.2
8	The effects of digital transformations are still there in our daily lives, and some will continue to coexist	152(152)	26(26)	22(22)	1	0.75

Table 4
Section-3: Importance of digital literacy in quality of education

1	Simple inquiries can be answered by students who have access to a computer and the Internet.	176(176)	8(8)	16(16)	3.9	0.84
2	Students must be able to distinguish between a reliable and an unreliable source.	155(155)	15(15)	30(30)	3.71	1.1
3	Students better comprehend the solutions they've uncovered and are pushing for new ways to apply what they've learned.	147(147)	35(35)	18(18)	3.89	1
4	Being a good digital citizen entails knowing how to utilize the internet and technology responsibly and appropriately.	153(153)	24(24)	23(23)	3.92	0.98
5	When used effectively and imaginatively, technology can help to bridge those gaps, such as in one-to-one classes.	157(157)	22(22)	21(21)	3.92	0.98
6	Thanks to technological advancements, teachers can now give their students an option in the type of work they make for assignments, such as a video, podcast, or written story.	143(143)	39(39)	18(18)	3.75	1.13
7	Digitally trained teachers also recognize that it is less about the technology than it is about the personalized experience that technology can deliver to each student.	160(160)	24(24)	16(16)	3.96	1
8	Good instructors understand how their pupils learn and engage with them, and they may utilize this knowledge to advocate for technology that will help them unlock new teaching possibilities.	151(151)	24(24)	25(25)	3.82	0.93
9	Given a student's familiarity with the tools and the varied forms within their culture, the content and the technologies employed may vary in efficacy.	158(158)	141(4)	28(28)	4	0.91

Table 5
Section-4: Teachers training for digital literacy

1	The most significant factor in improving teacher quality is training. Because every teacher's needs for in-service training are different,	168(168)	18(18)	14(14)	4	0.93
2	Professional development activities should be individualized and accessible to meet the needs of individual teachers.	153(153)	13(13)	34(34)	3.85	0.86
3	To make up for the lack of a good foundation, the Pakistani government has taken several steps, at least on a policy level, to increase the level and quality of teacher education.	156(156)	25(25)	17(17)	3.93	1.05
4	It possesses the most powerful instrument for creating teacher professional development to overcome flaws in the formal education system.	158(158)	22(22)	20(20)	3.95	0.96
5	Digital technology is the most often utilized ICT instrument for teacher training in digital literacy.	148(148)	24(24)	28(28)	3.8	1.0
6	Using video in teacher training enhanced the quality of the training and the learning results.	154(154)	23(23)	23(23)	3.92	0.97
7	The use of mobile phones in teacher training, which improves classroom practice and reaches teachers in rural areas, as well as in student assessment.	154(154)	16(16)	30(30)	3.97	0.87
8	Teacher education helps to ensure that students' cognitive and language abilities are up to par, resulting in better learning results.	165(165)	18(18)	17(17)	4.82	0.92

Table Description on the base of gender

Table 6

Statistical technique Independent Sample t. test was used to compare the male and female response about Situation Analysis of Digital literacy of the Teachers of Children with Multiple Disabilities and results were interpreted in below tables

Gender	N	M	SD	df	Sig.	t
Male	85	101.5	6.16	23	3.79	-1.02
Female	115	104.7	9.64	20.5		

*P > .05 Level of Significance

Table 6 indicates that the empirical information for males ($N=85$, $M=6.16$, $S.D.=6.16$) and for females ($N=115$, $M=104.7$, $S.D.=9.64$) with t-statistics ($t(23) = -1.02$, $*P > .05 = 3.79$) which leads to the decision that there is a significant difference in the situation analysis of digital literacy regarding the teacher of children with multiple disabilities based on gender (male/female). Moreover, it reveals that females have more knowledge than male respondents.

Table 7

The difference in the opinion among respondents about Situation Analysis of digital literacy of the teachers of children with multiple disabilities based on an area of rural or urban (Independent Sample t-test)

Area	N	M	SD	df	t	Sig.
Rural	37	111.24	7.98	198	-.254	.013
Urban	163	110.85	10.13	65.02		

*P > .05 Level of Significance

Table 7 indicates that the empirical information from rural ($N=37$, $M=111.24$, $S.D.=7.99$) and urban ($N=163$, $M=10.13$, $S.D.=10.13$) with t-statistics ($t(198) = -.254$, $*P > .05 = .013$) which leads to the decision that there is a significant difference in the situation analysis of digital literacy regarding the teacher of children with multiple disabilities based on respondent school area (rural/urban). Moreover, it reveals that urban respondents have more awareness.

Table 8

The difference in the opinion among respondents about Situation Analysis of digital literacy of the teachers of children with multiple disabilities based on the area of rural or urban (Independent Sample t-test)

Area	N	M	SD	df	t	Sig.
School	37	111.24	7.98	198	-.254	.013
Centre	163	110.4	10.13	65.02		

*P < .05 Level of Significance

Table 8 indicates that the empirical information from school ($N=37$, $M=111.24$, $S.D. = 7.98$) and from the center ($N=163$, $M=110.4$, $S.D. = 10.13$) with t-statistics ($t(198) = -.254$, $*P < .05 = .013$) which leads to the decision that there is a significant difference in the situation analysis of digital literacy regarding the teacher of children with multiple disabilities based on the respondent of (school/center). Moreover, it reveals that center respondents have more knowledge

Table 9

The difference in the opinion among respondents about Situation Analysis of digital literacy of the teachers of children with multiple disabilities based on the type of their designations (one way ANOVA test)

Designation	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	2029.14	4	507.28	5.89	.000
Within Groups	16924.73	195	86.79		
Total	18953.87	199			

*P < .05 Level of Significance

Table 9 indicates that the empirical information for Between Groups (Sum of squares=2029.14, $df=4$, Mean square=507.28) and for Within Groups (Sum of squares=16924.73, $df=195$, Mean square=86.79) with one way ANOVA ($F(199) = 5.89$, $P < .05 = .000$) which leads to the decision that there is a significant difference in the opinions of teachers about digital literacy.

Table 10

The difference in the opinion among teachers about Situation Analysis of digital literacy of the teachers of children with multiple disabilities based on Academic qualification (one way ANOVA test)

Experience	Some of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	2087.7	4	521.92	6.034	.000
Within Groups	16866.17	195	86.49		
Total	18953.87	199			

*P < .05 Level of Significance

Table 10 indicates that the empirical information for Between Groups (Sum of squares=2087.7, $df=4$, Mean square=521.92) and for Within Groups (Sum of squares=16866.17, $df=195$, Mean square=86.49) with one

way ANOVA ($F(199) = 6.034, P < .05 = .000$) which leads to the decision that there is a significant difference in the opinions of teachers about digital literacy.

Table 11

The difference in the opinion among teachers about Situation Analysis of digital literacy of the teachers of children with multiple disabilities based on Divisions of participants (one way ANOVA test)

Division	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	250.87	3	83.62	.876	.454
Within Groups	18703.0	196	95.42		
Total	1895.3	199			

* $P < .05$ Level of Significance

Table 11 indicates that the empirical information for Between Groups (Sum of squares=250.87, df=3, Mean square=83.62) and for Within Groups (Sum of squares=18703, df=196, Mean square=95.42) with one way ANOVA ($F(199) = .876, P > .05 = .454$) which leads to the decision that there is no significant difference in the opinions of teachers about digital literacy.

Findings & Conclusions

This study aimed to discuss the situational analysis of digital literacy for students with multiple disabilities. A three Likert scale survey was performed for this research, which included an insight into teachers' awareness of teacher about digital literacy, Implication of digital literacy, the importance of digital literacy in quality of education teachers training for digital literacy, and the impact of digital literacy in the everyday lives of people with disabilities. In this study, the researcher judges that digital literacy can help the student learn how to complete the task. Several assessments were noted.

Discussion and Recommendations

This study was directed to investigate the situational analysis of digital literacy for the teachers of the student with multiple disabilities awareness of assistive technology of teachers for children with disabilities in Punjab. Under the guidance of experts in special education, the researchers made a fruitful discussion at teachers' awareness about digital literacy. They discussed the advantage of digital literacy in the student's daily lives with a disability. The research showed that teachers are well aware of digital literacy and that digital literacy for disabled students in schools and public areas. Professionals agreed that digital literacy increases the ability and working of the student with a disability. Without digital literacy services, it is very difficult to educate children without digital literacy. It is recommended that Workshops and seminars should be arranged for the teachers of special education working in the special education institution government of Punjab to enhance the awareness level regarding digital literacy for the children with special needs. There must be a regular training schedule after a suitable period for teachers to update their knowledge about the usage of digital literacy for students with multiple disabilities.

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